

1st NEWSLETTER

LEE BED

Open Innovation Test Bed for development and production
of nanomaterials for lightweight embedded electronics

Budget:
€ 11.4 M

Duration:
4 years

Partners:
17 total with
4 Industrial cases

Website:
www.lee-bed.eu
Email: lee-bed@dti.dk

Bring your ideas and concepts to market through LEE-BED's three industrial phases, which will allow you to work with the leading European research and technology organizations and industry within nanomaterials, nano enabled formulations, and digital printing

IN THIS ISSUE:

About LEE-BED
LEE-BED phases
LEE-BED use cases
Phase assessments

News & Activities
Project Meetings
Conferences

Workshops
Clustering
Upcoming events
Project Partners

The LEE-BED project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 814485

ABOUT LEE-BED

LEE-BED is an open innovation test bed (OITB), which has been funded by Horizon 2020. The project started on 1st of January 2019, having a duration of 48 months. The project's aim is to form a sustainable OITB, offering its service to the European industry within the field of embedded and printed electronics.

The digitalisation of the European production industry through digital-based production technologies, such as ink-jet printing, additive manufacturing, robotically assisted in-mould labelling, laser processing, stereo-lithography, etc., requires functional nanomaterials and formulations and is a major bottleneck due to high prices and limited production volume.

LEE-BED will address these challenges by building European infrastructure for rapid development and pilot production of nanomaterial, inks, adhesives and composites as well as digital-based production pilot-lines pilot production lines. LEE-BED will unify the entire value chain from raw materials to embedded electrical components, providing tailored solutions for European entrepreneurs, start-ups, SMEs and large enterprises, with the main objective of going from concept to prototype within six months. LEE-BED will guide European industry towards sustainable implementation of innovative technologies, making them stronger and more competitive on a global scale.

LEE-BED PHASES

LEE-BED will bring ideas to market through three industrial phases, consisting of:

Phase 1 TECHNO-ECONOMIC MODELLING

The technological and economic assessment encompasses the technical evaluation of an idea, a "Life-Cycle Analysis" (LCA), safety, and regulatory tests as well as patent mapping.

Phase 2 PILOT PROJECT

The pilot project: Customers gain access to pilot lines for printing nanomaterials, nano-based formulations, and components in order to implement their ideas as initial prototypes and bring these prototypes into pilot production.

Phase 3 KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

Knowledge transfer: LEE-BED offers IPR (intellectual property rights), business planning, standardization and safety services and helps companies establish contact with potential investors.

Phase 1 MODELLING:

- I. Technical assessment
- II. Pre-safety assessment
- III. Economic assessment
- IV. Life cycle assessment
- V. Patent mapping

*Additional: Pilot project funding support

Phase 2 PILOT PROJECT:

- I. Nanomaterial pilot lines
- II. Formulation pilot lines
- III. Component pilot lines

Phase 3 KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER:

- I. IPR & patent services
- II. Standardisation services
- III. Business planning services
- IV. Investor contact services

INDUSTRIAL CASES

Smart decorative surface

Embedded environmental sensing
Wireless communication
Flexible backlighting

Functional automotive dashboard

Embedded touch sensing
Embedded lighting
Compatible with injections moulding and
thermal forming processes

Intelligent labels

Embedded temperature & humidity sensing
Anti-counterfeiting
Wireless communication
NFC sensors

Structural monitoring

Quality control and traceability
Embedded temperature and geolocalisation (tags) sensing
Embedded humidity, vibration and strain sensors
Wireless communications

PHASE 1 ASSESSMENTS

During April the Phase 1 assessment had the first deliverable for the LEE-BED use cases "Phase I assessment for MAIER, ACCIONA, GRAFIETIC and SWAROVSKI". This deliverable demonstrates the workflow of the phase 1 assessment and current status of services. According to the workflow the first step of the process is a common data collection sheet in order to collect all necessary data from customers. Subsequently, the phase 1 assessment is performed to

ascertain the feasibility of the customer's idea in technical, safety, economic, environmental & IP terms. It determines the benefits of bringing novel nanomaterials for embedded electronics in their products and production lines as well as mapping out the barriers for doing so. Following this assessment, stakeholders will have the opportunity to develop prototypes, up to TRL7, in pilot projects in phase 2, based on the outcomes of phase 1.

Technical assessment (TPU): This service will quantify the technical feasibility meeting LEE-BED user specifications through electromechanical and production design and modelling. This assessment will provide detailed information about nanomaterials, formulation and component pilot lines needed to perform the pilot project in phase 2.

Pre-safety assessment (ITENE): Safety and regulatory issues for both material and processes, based on the technical assessment, will be reviewed to determine any potential barriers that need to be addressed within the technical solutions presented.

Economic assessment (SIE): A business model canvas will be developed using the information provided through the technical assessment. The model will be used to ascertain the cost of the pilot project and to make a preliminary plan for the return of investment (ROI) and investment requirements for both the pilot project and the transfer of knowledge and technologies.

Life cycle assessment (FHG-IBP): LCA will be used to predict device-specific environmental impacts for each customer. Key of the sustainability evaluation is the identification of environmental impacts along the entire value chain including hotspots in the production and recyclability at the device end of life.

Patent mapping (DTI): To ascertain the state-of-the-art (SoA) within a field, patent mapping tools will be used, which can produce patent statistics based on geography, timing, etc. Main players, competing technologies and IP barriers will be the output of this mapping.

FACT BOOK (OUTCOME PHASE 1 ASSESSMENT)

After receiving all fact sheets from the service provider, they are compiled into the fact book and finalised, by including a summary of the phase 1 services. It serves as information for the customer as well as a basis for the subsequent phase 2.

TRANSFER TO EXTERNAL CUSTOMER

After an internal review from all service providers and LEE-BED contact person, ensuring its completeness and the comprehensibility, the fact book is transferred by the LEE-BED contact person to the customer.

NEWS & ACTIVITIES

PROJECT MEETINGS

22 JANUARY 2019

The Kick-Off Meeting of LEE-BED project coordinated by DTI, was held in the DTI premises in Copenhagen, Denmark. LEE-BED is one of the four "Open Innovation Test Beds for upscaling of lightweight materials" projects funded by the EC.

26/27 JUNE 2019

The 6M meeting of LEE-BED project took place at ITENE in Valencia, Spain. Partners discussed recent results and planned future activities.

21/22 JANUARY 2020

The 12M project meeting of LEE-BED took place at the facilities of TNO, in Eindhoven, The Netherlands. All participants discussed the advancements of their work presenting valuable outcomes and coordinating the next steps towards the implementation of the LEE-BED.

NEWS & ACTIVITIES

CONFERENCES

10-11.04.2019

Ecosystems for Innovation, Padova

The 2019 edition, dedicated to the Ecosystems for Innovation theme, had provide a 360-degree in-depth analysis of the networks for innovation, presented according to a broad and rich vision of new formats and contents.

15.11.2019

IDTechEx Berlin 2019

DTI participated IDTechEx Show to identify and commercialise the best opportunities for emerging technologies about LEE-BED Project

22.01.2020

From Science to Shelf: Innovating through Formulation

CPI has disseminated the LEE-BED project in Conference:Innovating through Formulation

29-31.07 and 01.08.2019

16th Annual International Conference on SMEs, Entrepreneurship and Innovation: Management – Marketing – Economic – Social Aspects

AXIA Innovation participated in order to disseminate the LEE-BED project. The aim of the conference is to bring together academics and researchers of all areas of Business, Economics, Management, Marketing, Accounting, Finance, Human Resources, MIS and Law, Entrepreneurship, Innovation, Technology and Industrial Dynamics

19.09.2019

15. Ökobilanzwerkstatt

The Fraunhofer Institute in cooperation with the IABP GaBi of the University of Stuttgart organized the 15th LCA workshop in Stuttgart, Germany. Fraunhofer IBP staff disseminated LEE-BED by exploring the sustainability potentials of printed electronics.

NEWS & ACTIVITIES

12.02.2020 PICK&PACK

ITENE presented at PICKPACK2020, which takes place in Barcelona, the KET technologies that will revolutionise the world of packaging, such as smart packaging and electronic printing. Additionally, ITENE has presented the European project LEE-BED Horizon, in order to establish an open innovation platform that supports the development of nanomaterials for printed electronics.

19 - 21.03.2019 LOPEC 2019: DRIVING THE FUTURE OF PRINTEDELECTRONICS

ITENE had disseminated the LEE-BED project with posters in a conference on the topic of organic and printed electronics

29.
NOV.
2019

Danish-Bavarian workshop on ICT in H2020

DTI and AXIA Innovation attended Danish-Bavarian Workshop in Robotics/ICT in H2020 organised by Bayfor. LEE-BED Project in presented towards more to 30 participating, topic of discussions includes widespread dissemination

27.
MAY.
2020

IDTechEX virtual: Opportunities for Printed & Flexible Electronics

SWAR gave a talk on "High and Lows of Printed Electronics on an End User's perspective" at the IDTechEx virtual conference focusing on "Opportunities on Flexible and Printed EElectronics", also highlighting their role in the LEE-BED-H2020 project.

CONFERENCES & WORKSHOPS

NEWS & ACTIVITIES

CLUSTERING EVENTS

02.
APR.
2019

“Open Innovation Test Beds – Introduction, Solutions and Networking” Workshop

AXIA Innovation attended the “Open Innovation Test Beds – Introduction, Solutions and Networking” Workshop that took place in Brussels. The workshop focused on bringing together representatives from all OITBs funded this far so that they may begin to share approaches, exchange best practices, and provide feedback as they proceed in establishing these services.

05.
MAY
2019

7th Tyrolean Network Meeting - Horizon 2020

The aim of the network meetings was the regular exchange of current topics and information about the EU funding program Horizon 2020. The event took place on the premises of Swarovski.

14-15.
NOV.
2019

1st clustering event of Open Innovation Test Beds (OITB) projects funded under the NMBP-01-2019 topic

AXIA Innovation and DTI were participating in the 1st clustering event of Open Innovation Test Beds project funded under the NMBP-01-2019 topic, related to lightweight materials. The target of the event is to discuss common issues of the projects such as the setup of the Single-Entry Point, Legal status of the OITB, business models, pricing policy and marketing activities.

NEWS & ACTIVITIES

CONGRESS

18-19.
NOV.
2019

AIPIA Active and intelligent Packaging

ITENE presented the LEE-BED Project in Active & Intelligent Packaging World Congress

AIPIA WORLD CONGRESS
November 18th - 19th, 2019

*DISRUPTING YOUR BRAND'S PACKAGING WITH THE LATEST
ACTIVE & INTELLIGENT TECHNOLOGIES*

Amsterdam

UPCOMING EVENTS

EVENT	PLACE	DATE	WEBSITE
LOPEC Driving The Future Of Printed Electronics	Munich	24-25 March 2021	https://www.lopec.com/en/
IDTechEx 3D Printing & 3D Electronics	Berlin	TBD	https://www.idtechex.com/ https://www.idtechex.com/3d-printing-europe/show/en/
Electronica	Munich	10 - 13 November 2020	https://electronica.de/en/
IEEE Nano	Canada	29 - 31 July 2020	https://2020.ieeenano.org/
MNE 2022	Belgium	September 2022	https://www.mne2020.org/
Pollutec	Lyon	1-4 December 2020	https://www.pollutec.com/en-gb.html

PROJECT PARTNERS

LEE
BED

The EU project LEE-BED brings together 17 European RTOs into an Open Innovation Test Bed. These RTOs come from the sphere of printed electronic components and are global leaders in their field. The innovation test bed already consists of these partners:

cpi

TNO

TU/e EINDHOVEN
UNIVERSITY OF
TECHNOLOGY

RI
SE

Fraunhofer

VSparticle

Sustainable
INNOVATIONS

AXIA INNOVATION

tpu

SWAROVSKI

grafietic
identificación y sistemas

acciona
Construction

SD Partners
DIGITAL PARTNERS

LinkedIn

Website:

www.lee-bed.eu

YouTube

DESIGN BY: AXIA INNOVATION

This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 814485